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1. Miroslav Ballay HOW TO GET TO KNOW UZBEKISTAN.....	7
2. Махмудова Г.Т. ЗАРАТУШТРА “ГОҲ”ЛАРНИНГ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРГА ЙЎНАЛТИРИЛГАН АКСИОЛОГИК КОНЦЕПЦИЯСИ.....	15
3. Қосимов Козимжон Исоқович ИЖОДКОР ШАХС ФАЛСАФАСИ ЁХУД “ЎТКАН КУНЛАР”НИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ- ФАЛСАФИЙ МОҲИЯТИ.....	23
4. Хакимова А.Х. ОБ ИСТОКАХ БУХАРСКОГО ШАШМАКОМА, О ЗАРАТУШТРЕ–АВТОРЕ ГАТ, О НАРОДЕ, ПЕВШЕМ КОЛЛЕКТИВНЫЕ ГИМНЫ О ШЕСТИ БОЖЕСТВАМ.....	30
5. Азизуллах Арал НАВОИЙ ЎЗИГА ҚЎЙГАН ҲАЙКАЛНИ БУЗИБ БЎЛМАС ЁХУД АФГОНИСТОНДАГИ НАВОИЙШУНОСЛИК ТАРИХИ.....	41
6. Жалалова Гулбахор Одилжонова ИННОВАЦИОН МУРАККАБЛИК: АКСИОЛОГИК МУАММОЛАР ВА ЯНГИ МЕТОДОЛОГИЯ ЗАРУРИЯТИ.....	49
7. Мадаева Мўътабархон Амануллаевна ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА МУМТОЗ ВА ЯНГИ ДАВР НАВОИЙШУНОСЛИК ТАРИХИ.....	54
8. Джураева Нигора Авазовна ОНТОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ЦЕННОСТНОГО ОТНОШЕНИЯ К БЫТИЮ.....	61

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Miroslav Ballay

Professor of Culture Studies (Prof.)

Institute of Culture and Tourism Management,
Cultural Studies and Ethnology Faculty of Arts,
Constantine the Philosopher University in Nitra

E-mail: mballay@ukf.sk

HOW TO GET TO KNOW UZBEKISTAN <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8020405>**ABSTRACT**

The author presents a variability of traveller modes, i.e. the manifold ways of how one can get an interpretation grasp of a visited country. In his traveller strategy, the author applies heuristic, aesthetic and performative modes. Conveying his experience of a beckoning country in the heart of Central Asia, he introduces the reader to the unique and rare expressiveness of Uzbekistan. Images of this cultural landscape locked in Central Asia as unveiled by him essentially constitute an experiential country reading supplemented with a deciphered interpretation.

Keywords: Central Asia, Uzbekistan, cultural area, communication, country, travel.

Мирослав Баллай

Профессор культурологии (Проф.)

Институт культуры и туристического менеджмента,
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E-mail: mballay@ukf.sk

КАК ПОЗНАКОМИТЬСЯ С УЗБЕКИСТАНОМ**АННОТАЦИЯ**

Автор показывает множество способов путешествия, то есть как можно по-разному интерпретировать ту или иную страну, которую посетил. При раскрытии и передаче информации о путешествиях автор применил эстетическую, образовательную и перформативную модели стратегии исследования путешествий. Он знакомит читателей с уникальной выразительностью Узбекистана, страной, располагающейся в самом сердце Центральной Азии, передает образы его культурного пространства, которые по сути являются восприятием того государства и интерпретацией той местности в коммуникативно-рецептивном смысле.

Ключевые слова: Центральная Азия, Узбекистан, культурное пространство, коммуникация, территория, путешествие.

Miroslav Ballay

Madaniyatshunoslik bo'yicha professor
Madaniyat va turizm menejmenti,
kulturologiya va etnologiya institute Falsafa fakulteti
Nitradagi Konstantin Faylasufi universiteti
E-mail: mballay@ukf.sk

O'ZBEKISTON BILAN QANDAY TANISHISH MUMKIN

ANNOTATSIYA

Muallif sayohat qilishning ko'plab usullarini, ya'ni tashrif buyurgan u yoki bu mamlakatni turli yo'llar bilan qanday talqin qilish mumkinligini ko'rsatadi. Sayohat haqidagi ma'lumotlarni yetkazishda muallif sayohat tadqiqoti strategiyasining estetik, tarbiyaviy va ijro modellarini qo'llagan. U kitobxonlarni Markaziy Osiyoning qoq bag'rida joylashgan O'zbekistonning o'ziga xos ekspressivligi bilan tanishtiradi, uning madaniy makonining timsollarini yetkazadi, ular orqali idrok etish va o'sha hududni kommunikativ-reseptiv ma'noda talqin qilishni ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: O'rta Osiyo, O'zbekiston, madaniy makon, aloqa, hudud, sayohat.

Introduction. This article aims to present travel strategies on the basis of a visit to Uzbekistan as part of the Erasmus+KA107 programme held on December 12-10, 2022 at the Department of Philosophy and Logic (National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek in Tashkent). By conducting an authentic exploration of an unknown cultural area, it shows various ways of how a traveller can grasp a destination as well as discourses concerning the *reading* of it. This is a travelogue of Uzbekistan – it unveils the culture of the everyday from the aesthetic level of reflection, through heuristic probing, up to performative realisation in this particular cultural area.

Methods and methodology. This travelogue chiefly uses methods of observation, heuristic probing, as well as reflection of a country within the framework of the so-called performative studies. The cultural landscape can be perceived inter-culturally, since as Slovak political scientist, journalist and pioneer of Slovak expedition tourism Svetozár Krno puts it: “Comparison of cultures is a fundamental method of acquiring knowledge.” [1, pp. 125]. The country reveals itself to the traveller through a powerful arsenal of signs. The traveller interprets the country as a text, literally. It is clearly a dynamic process of how one gets to know a destination. The cultural landscape is being projected into the recipient's mind as a valuable memory artefact [2], offering possibilities to make a cultural probe, but also engage in associative reading. The recipient inserts implicitly intuited content qualities into the country's texture as he is experiencing it. He often comes to see different discourses of reading the country, related to his own experiences of Central Asian realities. There are various travel modes as delineated stages of cultural terrain reconnaissance:

aesthetic – by absorbing Uzbek expressiveness

/exploration of the cultural landscape and architectural gems from the viewpoint of scenology/;

educational – by collecting heuristic materials from Uzbekistan's realities;

/natural conditions, history, language, religiosity, ethnicity, gastronomy/;

performative – by interactivity with the cultural otherness in its participatory manifestations

/wedding ceremonies, rituals, customs, conventions, taboos/.

Results and discussion. Uzbekistan attracts mainly with its cultural diversity. One frequently experiences a culture shock when they arrive in a foreign country, with the necessity of adapting oneself to a new, hitherto unknown environment. Slovak cultural scientist Viera Gažová points out that culture shock can be understood as a borderline form of intercultural contact, with this reaction being conditioned by sensitivity to cultural differences. In this context, she discusses, for example, the so-called acculturation stress, referring to Hofstede's description of culture shock. [3] A multitude of various stimuli, provoking the visitor with their novelty, contribute to the overall experience. One has to cope with novelty soon after arrival. The traveller is confronted with a foreign atmosphere,

linguistic and cultural differences, history and tradition, religiosity, ethnicity, natural environment, as well as the geopolitical position of contemporary Uzbekistan. [4]

In order to systematically experience the unknown cultural terrain of Central Asia, one can also help oneself by describing the so-called cultural landscape, or typology of cultural landscape, in the context of cultural geography. According to Slovak cultural and Romance studies scholar Jana Pecníková: “Cultural landscape can be presented as:

1. Real country – a country of fact, a space, place, town, territory,
2. Fantasy country – a country with a certain symbolic or spiritual significance, cultural legacy of myths, legends, symbols,
3. Ideal country – a country meeting certain criteria of the ‘ideal’ at a given time, an attempt to reshape the environment according to the ideal, as manifested, for example, in architecture dominated by a certain style” [5] The country is perceived as a whole, it is grasped holistically through a sum of various experiences. It becomes an object of exploration. The traveller not only becomes acquainted with the country, but actually reads it on the natural, geographical, linguistic, ethnic, religious, artistic and sociocultural levels. They interpret obvious meanings of the experienced cultural environment [6].

To map the country from the point of view of a traveller and aesthete is all about forming images of it. This is the case when the recipient simply lets himself be carried away by the country’s morphology. As a result, he sees rare images of the everyday life of Uzbekistan, multiplied by authentic experiences of the country. This is not just a matter of listing the usual sights of the world cultural heritage, but it is instead dominant aesthetic perception as one of the possible modes of grasping the landscape. The recipient creates, by reflecting the country, rare Uzbek expressiveness; for example, concerning the capital and other sites (Samarkand, Vabkent, Bukhara, Almazar).

The capital Tashkent is marked by an admirable patchwork of 20th-century modern architecture. It boasts, among other things, a rapid transit system – the only one in Central Asia with impressive decorations and original concepts for every single stop (such as *Alisher Navoiy*, *Mustquilliq Maidoni*, *Kosmonavtlar* and others). The city – which got a new face after a devastating earthquake – is an imaginary intertextual structure. Tashkent, in the context of the dominant cultural Central Asian complex, was also clearly influenced by Soviet urbanism. In this sense, the very city can be read as a text. According to Slovak philosopher and author Marek Debnár: “... Interactions between structures of a real city and a text also reflect the reader’s consciousness, with the text enabling him to find – beyond the boundaries of the everyday city – a different city, to which his dreams, memories or desires relate.”[7] The city can thus be conceived as a story. The visitor projects into it predictable contents formed, e.g., by study, knowledge, experiential reservoir, etc. Based on this, a “film” is created in the traveller’s mind as he immerses himself into the city’s structures as part of the acculturation process.

The experience of Tashkent was to a certain extent determined by the winter time, when the visit took place. The visitor could see several dimensions of the capital – a traditional Tashkent, an oriental and a Central Asian one [8] – a (post)Soviet Tashkent – a contemporary Tashkent, a globalised Tashkent [9] – an academic Tashkent, and – this was a bonus – a winter Tashkent with its distinctive lyrical poetics.

Buildings of modern architecture of the 20th century in Tashkent should be particularly highlighted – including, for example, Chorsu Bazaar, built on the site of the original bazaar in downtown Tashkent. It will certainly impress Slovak visitors immediately – especially those from Nitra – due to its striking resemblance to the Great Hall of the Slovak Agricultural University (SPU) in Nitra. Chorsu Bazaar is an important landmark of the city and one of its rarities. From the outside, it impresses with its dome shape including Islamic motifs. The inner outline of the walls in many ways resembles SPU’s Great Hall again: one can see the typical ribbing arranged in a star-like pattern around a circular oculus at the top of the vault [10, p. 147]. Both buildings reflect typical trends of modern architecture in the 20th century, not only of the former Eastern bloc. While the Nitra auditorium, designed by architect Vladimír Dědeček in the 1960s, is part of SPU’s university buildings, the Tashkent equivalent designed by architects Vladimir Azimov and Sabir Azylov from

1980 is a building combining oriental elements of Central Asia. This largest bazaar in Tashkent is in close proximity to the historic Islamic school (*Kukeldash Madrasah*) from 1570. Another striking landmark of this city is Hotel Uzbekistan, built again in the poetics of architecture prevalent in the second half of the 20th century.

The aesthetic leitmotif also prevails when one's foot enters other sites in Uzbekistan. The fairy-tale-mystical Samarkand provides an opportunity to experience historical stories from the times of the Timurid Empire by showcasing monuments, mausoleums, necropolises on a nearby hill above the city (Shah-i Zinda), gardens, observatories, mosques, religious schools (madrasah), prayer houses, squares, including Registan – “a square strewn with sand” [11, p. 442], which create a sensually intoxicating oriental whiff of Central Asia's exclusivity. This scent penetrates monuments of the World Heritage, which impress with their breath-taking majesty, stunning charm and magical expressiveness of the whole.

The expressive effect of Samarkand also originates from the massive slenderness and elegance of minarets, which ideally complement the monumentality of the sacred complexes. This style is unique in many ways, having developed during the era of the famous Timurid Empire. “Timur chose Samarkand as the place of his residence and made it into a dazzling centre of power and scholarship with many architectural gems. Architects and artists from all the conquered territories, from Asia Minor through Azerbaijan, the Caucasus, India, to Iran and beyond, were forced to take part in constructing colossal sacred and secular state buildings. While Timur was being driven by his desire to create monumental and magnificent buildings, the aforementioned approach brought together manifold artistic schools and traditions. A distinctive international style was developed there, now called the Timurid Empire style” [12, p. 416].

The blue Samarkand evokes a cold oriental mystique, especially in winter. This is due to the scenic effect of harmonious and symmetrically unified architecture. The contrast between human smallness and the magnificence one can see contains a great deal of transcendence. The experience of the city is also marked by these scenological parameters of decoding the buildings of high spiritual value and unique *genius loci*, all in an extraordinary scale.

A winter trip across Uzbekistan is in many ways a pilgrimage on the search of beauty. Wherever the visitor stops, they can perceive the stylistic uniqueness of architecture with sacred significance. Spiritual and aesthetic aspects of perception are constantly present at the same time.

The small, seemingly peripheral town of Vabkent (located 28 kilometres north of Bukhara) – consisting of a single main street – is triumphantly complemented by an imposing 11th- and 12th-century minaret and a mosque. By visiting this small town in Bukhara region one gets an apt opportunity to see, at least in part, the culture of everyday life in Uzbekistan. Individual dwellings line the regularly laid-out streets, which can be entered through dominant main gates. Mostly through these one enters the largely unifying atrium courtyards: a remnant of the ancient type of dwellings. The interior design of Uzbek houses is in many ways more modest than in Slovakia. A spacious room with no furniture and only a carpet makes a separate section. As Slovak aesthetician Petra Baďová puts it: “The carpet embodies the foundation on which we stand. Something earthly (biomorphic forms of ornament, dirt, and wear and tear of the material) meets here the heavenly (geometric order, harmony and purity of composition)” [13, p. 69]. Other parts of the inner courtyard around the perimeter of the atrium are designed for utilitarian ends – there is a kitchen, bedroom, toilet, etc.

The city of Bukhara, ancient and majestic, surrounded by the Kyzylkum Desert, is the epitome of charming oasis. The city, which withstood even the Mongol invasions, is a testimony to the miraculously preserved fortifications (Bukhara Citadel) as well as sacred Islamic architecture (e.g. Masjini-Kalyan Mosque, Mir-i Arab Madrasa, etc.).

Bukhara is astonishing, enigmatic and spiritual at the same time. It is literally “the Mecca of the East” [14, p. 111]. This makes it both immensely valuable and mysterious. It is especially captivating for its scenery of the almost fairy-tale unreality of the main architectural complex, the Po-i-Kalan (“Footprint of the Sublime”) [15, p. 436]. The dominant tower, called Minari Kalyan, has withstood the eruptions of time. This minaret, with its monumentality of enormous proportions, still evokes respect and reverence as a testimony of bygone ages. But it is chiefly the compactness of

ancient Bukhara that makes it so charming; it is its unity of composition, forms and styles, its perfection all around the place, with narrow streets featuring mosques, madrasas, khanaks, bazaars, palaces, as well as squares and gardens alternating. It is an ideal scene of a preserved, uniquely valuable medieval city.

Bukhara is a fairy-tale coulisse providing extraordinary opportunities to experience an aesthetic harmonious whole. The magical (mysterious) Bukhara in sunny, frosty, windy continental weather conditions is characterized by calm, wintery inertia. It captures the turbulent history, religiosity and the crossing of cultural exchanges of the Silk Road.

The educational travel modes are primarily related to the reading of the country and especially to the unpredictability of the entire cultural area. The connection to the Central Asian cultural complex is of key significance particularly when it comes to Uzbekistan. This context attunes the recipient to the optimal way of decoding a certain environment, region and space as an expressive semiosphere. Some particular geographical indicators are clearly predictable: the landscape, certain natural conditions, cultural history of a given area, etc. Before arriving, the recipient brings with him or her some stereotypical ideas about the destination, which are often distorting. According to Czech cultural scientist and ethnologist Barbora Půtová, this image of a destination is “a gnoseological category, being influenced by non-commercial sources, such as education, upbringing, statements of family and friends, magazines, newspapers and books” [16, p. 114]. Thus, there is a confrontation of the real and perceived with the expected and imagined. Svetozár Krno notes that the term Central Asia is not unambiguous. It usually comprises the area between the Caspian Sea in the west and China’s borders in the east. There is also an even broader term, especially in Anglo-Saxon literature: Middle Asia & Central Asia. According to Krno: “The broader term Central Asia, moreover, usually includes Altai, Eastern Sayan Mountains (Buryatia), Mongolia, Western China up to the Greater Khingan Mountains, Tibet, north-eastern Iran, northern Afghanistan, north-western India from the upper Indus Valley and the Brahmaputra, and possibly also western Pakistan” [17, p. 7]. The interior of Asia thus evokes certain closedness, confinement of a broad periphery. Uzbekistan, especially in the desert regions, evokes the expressive qualities of aridity. The recipient embarks on a semantic interpretation of the country, choosing something from the Central Asian reality for interpretive insight. They understand only what they communicate. They focus on the connection of the human being with the confronted culture, for unquestionably: “culture exists only because of human being, but at the same time culture somehow participates in the making of human being; meanwhile, human cultural activities significantly participate in changing the external environment as well as in creating a certain view of reality” [18, p. 47]. “The country then can be read as a social document or as an anthropological interpretation of a cultural text with a multitude of meanings.” [19, p. 47] It is understandable that not everything can or needs to be interpreted. According to Slovak cultural scientist Viera Gažová, “it is the mundane, the everyday that speaks to us most intensely; it is from these tiny, seemingly insignificant messages of triviality that the most striking milestones of our civilization are built. (...) One of the most prominent contemporary cultural scientists, C. Geertz, prefers an interpretative approach, which, according to him, perfectly suits the basic concept of culture, with this concept having a semiotic nature” [20, p. 234]. A country can thus be read layer by layer through its natural conditions, its historical developments, spirituality, language and ethnic structure, political, social and specific cultural climate [21].

Performative travel modes represent more action-oriented forms of interactivity of the traveller with the cultural site they visit. One of the ways of converging with local culture is by participating in individual performative practices used in the country for communication. An immensely valuable source for uncovering its uniqueness is, above all, the ceremonial, almost symbolic function of food (traditional cuisine) in the system of everyday life, but also, for example, in the context of a wedding, such as one attended in Almazar near Tashkent. The traveller not only becomes familiar with the traditional specialties of a particular region, but by tasting them they perceive the quality of the cultural terrain. Watching the preparation of food and the ceremonies associated with it, participating in dining, seeing the social etiquette and hearing the prayer after the meal are all phenomena when the culture is being unveiled in its integral performative manifestations.

In Uzbekistan, food is a very important instrument for ethnic identification, being strongly linked with cultural tradition and subject to religious rules. “The reception of food through taste could thus be perceived as one of the most intimate processes of receiving information from the environment (...) Eating is essentially a very intense internalization of information from the surrounding environment. From this point of view, it is no coincidence that food, as one of the most elementary social existential phenomena, becomes a direct part of artistic communication.” [22, p. 2 – 12]

Perhaps the most typical and traditional Uzbek food is the so-called *pilav* (*plov*, *osh*, *palau*, etc.). It is prepared and served in special restaurants, where people sometimes sit on the floor, which is not unusual in Uzbekistan. It is a special risotto made of beef or mutton, rice, carrots, onions, chickpeas, raisins, etc. It is cooked in a large cauldron outside the restaurant over a direct flame (ideally) or gas fire as the case may be. This national dish is prepared ceremonially, literally, and individual elements of the process must be strictly observed. Uzbeks are proud of this food and show it to their guests. Traditionally, it is served with bread, which in Uzbekistan has the shape of a round decorative piece. It is flat bread about 30 centimetres in diameter, which is baked in a clay oven in front of the customers and tastes like a cake [23, p. 114]. Uzbek bread (*non*) is round in shape and is baked stuck to the inner walls of the oven. The baker must obviously be skilled enough to be able to make it. Similarly, *samosas*, i.e. baked pastry bags filled with meat, are also prepared by sticking the dough to the heated oven walls. Samosa, popular throughout the entire Central and South Asia, is also widespread as street food in Uzbekistan.

Drinking green tea in teahouses (*chaikhanas*) is an essential part of Uzbek social life. Tea is drunk exclusively from bowls, with the first dose to be poured back into the teapot, as the local custom goes. In restaurants, before each main course of food, a basket of round traditional bread is placed on the table and the host tears it by hand into equally sized pieces. Tea is sipped as one eats the main meat dish (such as *shashliks*) with bread.

Another performative travelling experience was the unique opportunity of attending as a guest an authentic Uzbek wedding in Almazar near Tashkent. Special wedding houses (*tuyxona*) are designed just for this purpose in Uzbekistan, being able to harbour hundreds of guests. A typical Uzbek wedding cannot be viewed entirely from the Slovak perspective. Initially, the wedding party is similar to ours – it features dance, live music, wedding food, musical productions with an emcee, the reading of wishes, the presentation of gifts, etc. Nevertheless, there are some obvious differences, which are understandably the result of different cultural traditions. One noteworthy element is the strict separation of men and women throughout the wedding. While the women are inside the wedding house, the men wait outside until the bride and groom arrive. Accompanied by traditional music featuring the shalmai trumpet and drum, the crowd of men, along with the couple, make their way to the inside of the ceremonial house. Nevertheless, men and women remain separate as they sit down at round laid tables with varieties of Uzbek specialties: cold bowls, fruits, vegetables, nuts, cakes, roasted chicken wings and green tea. For starters, samosa is a must. Other courses include fish soup, for example, or beef gravy with rice, among others.

It is also interesting to see that the groom and the bride sit on an elevated position overlooking the entire hall in a literally fixed position (they place their right hand on the heart as a sign of respect and gratitude). While the gifts are being handed over, men and women, still separated, dance to Uzbek disco music. Nevertheless, the bride and groom do not dance at all and just overlook the entire wedding feast. There is also a rare custom of dancing with women or men – both groups remaining separate – passing banknotes from hand to hand.

At weddings, it is also possible to see stylized performances of traditional Uzbek *lazgi* dances and especially the Andijan polka in unique female and male versions. The apparent epilogue of the wedding party includes the escorting of the bride and groom, who leave the wedding reception by car to spend the wedding night. The guests then also return to their homes and the party ends before midnight.

Conclusion. Obviously, a short stay in Uzbekistan as part of the Erasmus+KA107 programme was not enough for getting deeper knowledge about the country. Residency is *de facto* learning *in* a country – or learning *by* a country, meaning that the country itself is the teacher. The planned

academic mobility event eventually became a significant opportunity for active learning. From the visitor's point of view, not only the sights of the world cultural heritage, but also rare expressiveness of everyday life in contemporary Uzbekistan came into the centre of attention. One's own empirical experience from a section of the country became available to project specific images of it – it was an **aesthetic mode of travel**. The residency can be conceived in this sense as a heuristic probe, a mapping of Central Asian cultural realities – this was an **educational mode of travel**, but there was also an interaction with it – and this was a **performative mode of travel**. These were different degrees of profiling the traveller's appropriation of the destination, as well as of discourses on how it is possible to *read* a country. They are good examples of how travel in its dynamic-continuous and processual aspects can look like.

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МАРКАЗИЙ ОСИЁ РЕНЕССАНСИ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖИЛД 4, СОН 1

ЖУРНАЛ РЕНЕССАНСА ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ

ТОМ 4, НОМЕР 1

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УШБУ ЖУРНАЛ ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ИННОВАЦИОН РИВОЖЛАНИШ
ВАЗИРЛИГИ ТОМОНИДАН МОЛИЯЛАШТИРИЛГАН А-ОТ-2021-11-СОНЛИ
“ЎЗБЕК ХАЛҚИ ДИНИЙ ВА МИЛЛИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРИ КОМПЛЕКСИНИНГ
ЭЛЕКТРОН-ТРАНСДИЦИПЛИНАР ПЛАТФОРМАСИНИ ЯРАТИШ” НОМЛИ
ИННОВАЦИОН ЛОЙИХА ДОИРАСИДА НАШРГА ТАЙЁРЛАНГАН.

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Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Тадqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000